

IMPORTANT FACTORS OF THE PROCEDURE, DURATION AND CARE OF EMERSON OF MILK TEETH IN CHILDREN.

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Annotation: In this article, the order and the process of eruption of milk teeth in children are presented, and parents should first help children in this process, as well as opinions on feeding procedures.

Keywords : Milk teeth, follicles, diagram . premolars diametric, trend , root , high and bottom , molars , brush , statistics , saliva , tissues , mineralization

Of the teeth in children appearance long and difficult process _ Babies most of the time unpleasant symptoms with together comes : pain , swelling , fever , but milk sting appear when and when it changes to new (permanent) , parents to them help to give can _ All to questions answers in my article illuminated .

20 teeth in children buds (follicles) of the mother in the womb harvest will be - from them temporary units develops . First , the teeth cut - dentoalveolar each of the hardware in line four piece _ This process in a child from 5-6 months starting from in the center bottom teeth appear to be with starts from 1-2 months after those above to the child rises . Only 4 lateral cutters tooth have - they to the central ones near located _ Baby's high part , maybe 9-11 months , lower appear in part 11-13 will be. Tooth teeth chase so the baby tooth teeth comes out

Babies for toothpicks

Wolf teeth shoot process usually lasting 2 months that 's enough time during baby saliva increased . Jaw skin bother not to do for him constant respectively wipe , protect cream with lubrication need _ From the child's place posture , nose leak and wet cough can _ From this except , temperature not only the first molar milk teeth jump out when it comes out , maybe the child is 9 to 12 years old has been constant molars appear himself anyway _ manifestation to do can _

It's understandable : a tooth meat swollen when gone , blood flow when it gets stronger and biological active substances in the body synthesis do it when he started , his main task swelling no to do and pathology no is to do Otherwise by doing in other words , the body is a disease as of the teeth appear to be effect does , as a result temperature rises .

When high temperature doctor to the child Paracetamol or based on Ibuprofen antipyretic preparations order it is possible while pain no syndrome _ does _

The majority only constant tooth root yes , temporarily while they think no , that 's why for it is easy down goes _ This is the idea wrong , everyone 's roots and nerves there is and they are constant to structure than much complicated to structure have , therefore for them treatment more difficult . Temporarily teeth less mineralized , their size smaller , blue to color have , softer and roots weaker . From this except their _ only 20 of them there are 32 of them

constant if a person has 28 pcs to know teeth if not. Temporarily tooth drop off time when it comes to his root melts , crown while by itself down goes , or doctor by fast and without pain respectively take thrown away Permanent the root is them when appear will be Permanent bite from 5-6 to 12-15 appear be usually begins with this _ time inside whole teeth out goes , though in some they are 30 years old after jump out in some cases while in general it won't be . They are fell in order grows . Permanent of molars appear to be process control to do if they are 3 months old after appear when , this serious pathology , for example , metabolic disease , vitamin deficiency or rickets to show can _ In children constant of the teeth of cracking this scheme proof gives _ But pathology didn't happen in case of the teeth appear to be sequence constant to be need _ From the beginning from , the child is 6-7 years old when full , the first constant teeth (" six " teeth) whole milk of the line behind jump out comes out They are milk teeth never when did not grow in the place appear will be Then temporarily teeth constant to the teeth is replaced , as is they are how came out if so , that's it in order . First , both of the jaw two tooth hole will change , then again two of them . Of them after small teeth (" fours ") or premolars jump out comes out They are children from 9 to 11 years old when it was changes , the second premolar or " fifth " to 12 years full until eruption need _ Teeth 13 years old unpaid jump out comes out Dental prosthesis At the end of them from scratch followed by the second big teeth (" seven ") erupt comes out They are 14 years old until changes. Third tooth teeth , " eight " or " wisdom ." teeth " last times jump out comes out In some they are 15 years old before appear will be in others much later , in others they are in general not to be possible. Permanent teeth small (premolar) and big (gear tooth) to is divided . Adult reached 8 in a person small teeth have , each of them 4 above and 4 teeth below there is Theirs main task the food grind and is grinding. They fell of molars in place appear will be Premolars big tooth and of the teeth features unites _ They are rectangles to the shape have _ to chew on the surface crack with There are 2 distinct tubercles . High of the jaw small teeth shape similar , but the first premolar is from the second a little bigger and to 2 roots has , in the second only one there is a root. Bottom premolars round are , each of them from 1 root consists of They are volume in terms of difference does : first premolar slightly smaller . Big teeth second of premolars behind grows . Theirs two of them from two , two of them in two . Most big " six " . High the first and second tooth There are 3 teeth , lower " sixes " and " sevens " have 2 roots . Third high and bottom of the teeth structure form and root from each other the number with difference does _ In some in general no _ Very rarely in cases , the rule as , east equatorial race in representatives addition the fourth molars occurs If temporary tooth in place constant tooth came out if and milk yet if not , doctor him take to throw advice gives _ First milk teeth biting very exciting process , especially parents for , children usually mothers , fathers and to grandmothers than easier patience they do Everything 20 pieces of milk tooth lies , constant teeth - 32. Usually , the first milk of the teeth eruption baby of life the third in the month starts and only three at the age of ends _ Teeth teeth loss and loss time in the table sure reflection reached _ Of course , in life very a lot exceptions there is Sometimes children one or two tooth with is born , often they are of life the first in weeks jump out comes out If the teeth to eat interrupt if not and very motionless if not (they falling down fall possible if) , then you worry don't take it without yourself children to the dentist show me

The tooth is delayed and the first tooth per year closer it turns out, from this worrying thing no, maybe from offspring to the offspring passable characteristic - panic to do don't hurry, grandma the first tooth my mother, father, uncle and from my aunt when that it came out to ask it is good. By the way, statistics information according to girls most of the time from development ahead, son children and, on the contrary, behind are staying. Everyone thing to age looking balance. Of the teeth delay early born in babies, often ill rickets _ _ with observed. Pay attention to this give _

Many children for teeth biting process much calm down is only _ short at times worry the mood increases increases, sleep and eating is broken. Well, that's it disease not but _ nature by provided natural is a process. Rarely less cases teeth biting difficult _ Small growth baby's body temperature teeth biting with depends to be can _ The pain loss for you tooth to the meat any one pill your rub and alcohol drinks solutions your application possible not _ in the pharmacy children for special anesthetic gel buy get is better.

Teething _ all the children to worry that puts thing is this breath get and something to chew desire _ Unnecessary from washing keep for trinket tie and sleep when you lie down, dust swallow fabric your head under put _ of the skin scratching feature and inflammation road not to put for of the child face down flowing from saliva wipe take _ To your mouth win who sends or small into pieces by biting will receive Dangerous things not to fall trust harvest do it For " Bite ". from the pharmacy special tooth the rings buy get is better. them to the child from giving before they are to the refrigerator no, short to time is placed, etc without they are very hard will be and baby to the jaw injury deliver can _ Liquid inside has been the rings buy not get better sometimes _ they are cracked goes _ Sometimes adults to the finger wearing special silicone brush with tooth meat a little massage can _ Same that's it brush up to about 10-12 months jump out came out teeth cleaning for is used. From this besides, microbes take to throw for tooth meat chamomile to the tincture dipped napkin with your wipe possible. Nutrition about First of the teeth appear to be with the child feeding process change starts _ First tooth with suck reflex biting and biting necessity with is replaced, therefore for now only liquid and soft food indispensable is considered Each _ in feeding to your child one a piece dried bread, whole soft until unripe a piece cucumber or carrots, not apples out of four one part skin and seedless give _ Chewing tooth of meat blood with to be provided improves, appears has been teeth teaches and strengthens and eruption need of those who to eat improves. Food of products consistency small, then bigger into pieces have has been from mashed potatoes to the patch change start need _ Food of products This " magnification " is different age children for industry in canned goods there is Good to chew ability is _ central nerve system of well-being from the signs is one This skill neurological problems has been children for easy not, but they are for this very important _ Chewing custom not only healthy digestion do maybe _ sure Articulation is clear of speech is the key. Baby in the period " in the mouth Porridge " was children hard from food according to porridge and potatoes puree preferred have seen

Healthy milk teeth how to look have

Get out gone milk teeth initially small and sharp, wavy edge unevenly, to each other near standing, yellow to color have _ Jaws growth with one in line, teeth also grow goes, approx four at the age of they are between cracks appear will be approx six year inside they are between already big spaces is available _ norm, this of the jaws enough level growth pace and their bigger constant of the teeth to shoot readiness shows. With age milk teeth more and

more unpleasant to look have - their work term ends. In the tooth to spots attention to give worth it White and black spots - initial characters caries , prevention get or treatment for tooth to the doctor appeal to do need _ Yellow-brown spots enamel hypoplasia (less development) are signs , they pedigree to be possible or during the prenatal period mother's bad eating or diseases because of appear to be can _ Milk teeth of enamel hypoplasia often occurs and constant those who are as usual jump out it turns out , that's why for you in advance don't worry need _ Fulfillment need the only thing is the child to the dentist show _ calcium of additions addition prescription required _ possible. Tissues mineralization break tetracycline pregnant to women face even when commanded to give can _ Tetracycline placenta from the barrier passes . It is enamel , dentine and to the bones easily attached to the teeth remains and their color changes - " tetracycline teeth ". On this basis of pregnancy last six in the month tetracycline is not ordered . Six from monthly starting from in the child this the drug apply not only in milk big tooth teeth , maybe that's it period harvest has been constant to paint the teeth too take will come of life initial five in the year to the children tetracycline don't give

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